

Application of Pedagogical Coaching Methods in Teaching Foreign Language to Students

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Abstract. *This article reveals important opportunities that allow the implementation of the main ideas of pedagogical coaching in teaching students a foreign language in the educational space of a modern university. These opportunities are considered in accordance with the main trends noted in the development of the higher education system of our country in recent years. At the same time, both positive and negative trends in its development are taken into account. Various examples of learning tasks used within this methodology are considered.*

Keywords: *Pedagogical coaching, Coaching method, communicative competence, communication, activity.*

Introduction: Based on the analysis of a wide range of specialized literature, the need to introduce pedagogical coaching into the process of teaching foreign languages to students has been proven as one of the important conditions for the further modernization of the modern local higher education system.

The purpose of this article is to consider the practical mechanisms of implementing the ideas of pedagogical coaching in teaching students a foreign language.

- 1) studying the possibilities of pedagogical coaching in the process of teaching foreign languages to students;
- 2) review of the system of person-oriented tasks in a foreign language;
- 3) review the system of requirements for the implementation of pedagogical coaching ideas in the process of teaching a foreign language.

At the current stage of the development of the higher education system of our country, we must admit that there are a number of trends that have a negative impact on learning a foreign language in higher education institutions. This includes:

- a decrease in the motivation of students to work regularly as part of their studies in the relevant subject, compared to previous generations;
- presence of a language barrier, fear of starting to speak the target language;
- often — students do not have enough time for independent education in a foreign language;
- most of the students do not have the opportunity to practice the language outside the educational area of the university. On the one hand, taking into account the presence of trends that have a negative effect on the acquisition of a foreign language by students and the increasing importance of its quality teaching, on the other hand, the search for innovative methods of teaching the relevant subject is becoming especially urgent.

Main part: When carrying out such a search, teachers, researchers and practitioners should not forget that the main goal of learning a foreign language in modern conditions is to develop communication skills that allow students to actively use the language they are learning in everyday life. At the same time, it is appropriate to choose pedagogical methods that take into account the individual characteristics of students' cognitive activity and allow them to use their creative abilities. In addition, when choosing one or another innovative educational technology, a modern teacher should remember that in today's society there is an indispensable need to develop common cultural skills among future graduates of the university, which will allow them to communicate and cooperate with representatives of other cultures. The above requirements are usually fulfilled by pedagogical coaching, which is the subject of this article.

It is known that pedagogical coaching means opening up a person's potential to increase his efficiency. When using this method, the teacher does not teach, but rather helps the students to learn. According to modern pedagogical research, about 80% of students' future success in learning a foreign language is their motivation and interest in the learning process.

Coaching in pedagogy is a relatively new approach that has been actively developing in recent decades. However, its origin can be traced in various fields of pedagogy and psychology.

One of the origins of coaching in pedagogy is humanitarian psychology aimed at developing a person and his potential. Ideas such as self-awareness and self-determination from humanistic psychology became the basis for the development of coaching in pedagogy.

Positive psychology also had a significant impact on the development of coaching in education. It is aimed at studying the positive aspects of human life, such as happiness, well-being and achieving goals. Coaching pedagogy uses the principles of positive psychology to help students achieve their goals and develop their potential.

The self-determination theory developed by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan also influenced the development of coaching in education. He asserts that humans have a desire for self-determination and self-actualization, and these needs must be met in order to achieve optimal development. Pedagogical coaching helps students identify their goals and develop an action plan to achieve them.

The origins of the development of coaching in pedagogy can be found in other areas such as psychotherapy, management and sports training. All these resources contribute to the formation and development of coaching in pedagogy, making it an effective tool for improving students and realizing their potential. Coaching pedagogy is based on several principles that help students achieve their goals and develop their potential. The positive results of coaching in pedagogy are focusing on the student. Coaching helps students identify their goals, develop an action plan, and help. The student is an active participant in the process and makes decisions based on his own factors. Plays the role of supporting and encouraging the student in pedagogy. It helps the student overcome obstacles, develops self-confidence and supports him in the process of achieving goals. A coach also helps the student find inner motivation and incentive to learn and develop.

Conclusion: Pedagogical coach actively listens to the student, sympathizes with his needs and feelings. He seeks to understand the student and their unique situation in order to offer the best solutions and approaches. Active listening and empathy help the student feel understood and supported. Pedagogical coach asks the student questions that help develop critical thinking, self-analysis, thinking. The questions help students recognize their strengths, overcome their weaknesses, and find new ways to solve problems. Feedback helps the learner learn from their mistakes and grow. Pedagogical coaching flexibly adapts to the student and his needs. He takes into account the individual characteristics of each student and suggests the most effective approaches to achieving his goals. Adaptability and adaptability help the student feel comfortable and confident in the learning process. These principles of coaching pedagogy help students improve their skills, achieve success, and become independent and confident individuals.

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